

HadISDH.marine Update Document

Kate Willett (MOHC), 4th April 2025

General Notes:

The HadISDH.marine.1.6.1.2024f contains all 12 months of 2024. There are no major changes (X), no bug fixes or minor changes (Y), and no minor bug fixes but an additional complete year of data is added from ICOADS.3.0.2, resulting in incrementing the Z element of the version number to 1.

Keep up to date with subsequent changes and analyses at

<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2025/04/2024-update-from-hadisdhmarine1612024f.html>.

Version Number X.Y.Z.0000p/f:

1.6.1.2024f

Major changes X:

- None

Bug fixes and minor changes Y:

- None

Minor bug fixes / historical data updates Z:

- Additional year of data (Jan to Dec 2025)

Start Date DD.MM.YYYY: 1973-01-01

End Date DD.MM.YYYY: 2024-12-31

Hadisdh Data Format (Baseline documentation): <https://zenodo.org/records/15357353>

Reference: No change

- Willett, K. M., Dunn, R. J. H., Kennedy, J. J., and Berry, D. I. 2020: Development of the HadISDH marine humidity climate monitoring dataset. Earth System Science Data. 12, 2853-2880, doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-2853-2020.
- Freeman, E., S.D. Woodruff, S.J. Worley, S.J. Lubker, E.C. Kent, W.E. Angel, D.I. Berry, P. Brohan, R. Eastman, L. Gates, W. Gloeden, Z. Ji, J. Lawrimore, N.A. Rayner, G. Rosenhagen, and S. R. Smith, 2016: ICOADS Release 3.0: A major update to the historical marine climate record. Int. J. Climatol. (doi:10.1002/joc.4775).

Other notes: The HadISDH update/analyses blog is here:

<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2025/04/2024-update-from-hadisdhmarine1612024f.html>.